

THE CONCEPT OF CONSCIOUSNESS IN THE APPROACHES OF DIFFERENT SCIENTISTS.

Bozorova Gulmira Mahmudovna

National University of Uzbekistan

The Faculty of Social Sciences

II Master's student of the Department of Philosophy and Logic

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Annotation: This article reflects the concept of consciousness in the approaches of different scientists in the history of philosophy. In this article, not only the concept of consciousness has been well analyzed but also revealed the notion of Consciousness in David Chalmers's philosophy.

Key words: Consciousness, perceptions, self-consciousness, analyses, definitions, Ability, to focus on, contemplation, awareness

Consciousness is the enormous secret in the many spheres of life. It could be the largest wonderful impediment in our investigation for a scientific understanding of the universe. Consciousness has different meaning; having of perceptions, thoughts, and feelings; awareness and so on.

The earliest English language uses of "conscious" and "consciousness" date back, however, to the 1500s. The English word "conscious" originally derived from the Latin *consciū* (*con-* "together" and *scio* "to know"), but the Latin word did not have the same meaning as the English word—it meant "knowing with", in other words, "having joint or common knowledge with another".¹ [1 Samuel Johnson A Dictionary of English Language. 1756.]

The philosophical literature on consciousness is quite unplanned and unsolved with seemingly independent strands talking about related problems without making contact with each other. The term is impossible to define except in terms that are unintelligible without a grasp of what consciousness means. Many fall into the trap of confusing consciousness with self-consciousness—to be conscious it is only necessary to be aware of the external world.² [1 Roche, Philippe "Five levels of self-awareness as they unfold early in life" *Consciousness and Cognition*. 2003]. Consciousness, at its simplest, is sentience or awareness of internal and external existence. Despite millennia of analyses, definitions, explanations and debates by philosophers and scientists, consciousness remains puzzling and controversial, being "at once the most familiar and the most mysterious aspect of our lives". Perhaps the only widely

¹ Samuel Johnson A Dictionary of English Language. 1756.

² Roche, Philippe "[Five levels of self-awareness as they unfold early in life](#)" *Consciousness and Cognition*. 2003

agreed notion about the topic is the intuition that consciousness exists.³[The Encyclopedia of Diderot & d'Alembert Collaborative Translation Project. Translated by Scott St. Louis.]

Consciousness is an intriguing but evasive circumstance: it is not possible to specify what it is, what it does, or why it evolved. Anything not worth reading has been written about it. The term "consciousness" is imprecise, referring to a number of happening. Sometimes it is used to refer to cognitive dimensions, such as the ability to introspect or to report one's rational issues. Sometimes it is cautiously tied to our ability to focus contemplation, or to voluntarily direct our behavior, feelings and awareness. Since 2010 or so, however, philosophical debates of attention have become more widespread, so it makes sense to discuss it in connection to consciousness, even if only briefly. Before the 1990s, "consciousness" was a term that scientists tried to stay away from it. It was considered as unscientific, as there was no respectable way to give it a satisfactory operational definition, i.e., it was difficult to give a definition that was grounded in empirical evidence. Back then, scientists studied attention instead, as it was easier to quantify it, or so it seemed. Empirical studies of attention have been fruitful since the 1960s. Now, although scientists tried hard to avoid talking about consciousness explicitly, it was not possible to ignore it entirely. For example, when psychologist Max Coltheart defines "visible persistence", it is hard to understand what we should mean by "visible" if it is different from "consciously seen," though there can indeed be other interpretations, such as "able to be seen." But one wonders whether that should mean "able to be *consciously* seen." Of course there are subtleties here; for example, Block further distinguishes between visible persistence and phenomenal persistence, which makes one wonder how to understand visible persistence exactly⁴. [Block, Ned. "Consciousness, Accessibility and the Mesh between Psychology and Neuroscience." *Behavioral and Brain Sciences* 30: 2007. P. 481-548.] But in any case, before the 1990s or so, attention was widely studied by scientists, and in a way it served as a surrogate for consciousness, as attention is more scientifically respectable according to many. The situation has dramatically changed. Nowadays consciousness studies are pervasive not only in sciences but also in philosophy. The reasons for this are complicated; it is not simply because nowadays consciousness can be better defined in sciences. Now

³ The Encyclopedia of Diderot & d'Alembert Collaborative Translation Project. Translated by Scott St. Louis.

⁴ Block, Ned. 2007. "Consciousness, Accessibility and the Mesh between Psychology and Neuroscience." *Behavioral and Brain Sciences* 30: 481-548.

the question concerning the relation between attention and consciousness arises: Are they identical? If not, how do they relate to each other? It is hard to maintain that they are identical, as there seem to be clear cases in which a subject, not necessarily a human subject, can focus its attention while being unconscious of the target. Perhaps that subject is a simple organism that is not conscious in the relevant sense, but arguably it has certain basic attention capacities, i.e., they can deploy their cognitive resources to focus on specific targets. Normally the question is more about whether attention is necessary and/or sufficient for consciousness. Jesse Prinz argues for this strong view, and sometimes he comes close to the identity view. This view faces two basic challenges: Some have argued that attention is not necessary for consciousness; the phenomenological overflow view held by Block is one such view. Some have argued that attention is not sufficient for consciousness; Robert Kentridge and colleagues have argued that the case of blind sight—patients who are blind in certain parts of their visual fields due to cortical damages—is attention without awareness, since these patients exemplify clear markers of attention, while the patients themselves also insist that they are unconscious of the relevant parts of the visual fields. Now, these are all highly debatable and there is much room to disagree. Both consciousness and attention are still heated topics nowadays, and will continue to be so in the foreseeable future.

The noun “consciousness” has an equally diverse range of meanings that largely parallel those of the adjective “conscious”. Distinctions can be drawn between creature and state consciousness as well as among the varieties of each. One can refer specifically to phenomenal consciousness, access consciousness, reflexive or meta-mental consciousness, and narrative consciousness among other varieties. There were, however, many occurrences in Latin writings of the phrase *conscius sibi*, which translates literally as “knowing with oneself”, or in other words “sharing knowledge with oneself about something”. This phrase had the figurative meaning of “knowing that one knows”, as the modern English word “conscious” does. In its earliest uses in the 1500s, the English word “conscious” retained the meaning of the Latin *conscius*.

For example, Thomas Hobbes in *Leviathan* wrote: “Where two, or more men, know of one and the same fact, they are said to be Conscious of it one to another. The Latin phrase *conscius sibi*, whose meaning was more closely related to the current concept of consciousness, was rendered in English as “conscious to oneself” or “conscious unto oneself”.⁵ [*Thomas Hobbes Leviathan: or, The*

Thomas Hobbes Leviathan: or, The Matter, Forme & Power of a Commonwealth, University Press. p. 39. 1904.)

Matter, Forme & Power of a Commonwealth, University Press. p. 39. 1904.] A basis for consciousness has also been sought in the *holistic* nature of quantum mechanics and the phenomenon of *entanglement*, according to which particles that have interacted continue to have their natures depend upon each other even after their separation. Unsurprisingly these models have been targeted especially at explaining the coherence of consciousness, but they have also been invoked as a more general challenge to the atomistic conception of traditional physics according to which the properties of wholes are to be explained by appeal to the properties of their parts plus their mode of combination, a method of explanation that might be regarded as unsuccessful to date in explaining consciousness.

Descartes reported his conscious experiences in his *Meditations on First Philosophy*. These figured centrally into his arguments that he has a mind. Behaviorism, materialism, functionalism, and property dualism seek to explain our mental lives, so they will need to include consciousness, as it is one of the most important elements of mentality. Qualia and raw feels are one way to understand consciousness; since they have been covered earlier, we will not discuss them here.

The mind is one thing that has always fascinated and puzzled us. It is the only thing that we can be certain of existing, yet, apparently, we do not know exactly what it is, how it occurs, and why it occurs. ⁶[Armstrong, David. 1968. *A Materialist Theory of the Mind*. London: Routledge.]

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The issue of consciousness stands uneasily at the door of science and philosophy. I would have to say that it is properly a scientific subject matter: it is a natural phenomenon like motion, life, and cognition, and calls out for explanation in the way that these do. But it is not to prove to investigate by the usual scientific methods. Nowadays consciousness studies are pervasive not only in sciences but also in philosophy. The reasons for this are complicated; it is not simply because nowadays consciousness can be better defined in sciences.

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